

Implementation fidelity measurement

We argue that the levels of fidelity can be categorized with three levels: Low fidelity, medium fidelity and high fidelity. Based on reference values from the study protocol, a scoring system was devised to categorize the values of each of the variables within one of three fidelity categories (Table 1).

Table 1: Levels of fidelity: variable reference values and fidelity scores

	Low Fidelity	Medium Fidelity	High Fidelity	Medium Fidelity	Low Fidelity
<i>Content and coverage</i>					
Number of sessions	1 – 3	4 – 5	6 - 8		
<i>Frequency and duration</i>					
Timely start ¹			0 - 60	61 - 75	≥76
Duration ²	0 - 8	9 -12	13 - 21	22 - 25	≥ 26
Timely completion ¹	-150 - -50 ³	-49 - -31	- 30 – 0	1 – 15	≥16

A value within the category low fidelity was awarded 0 points, values within medium fidelity gives 1 point, and values within high fidelity gives 2 points.

The construction of a composite score outlining the levels of implementation fidelity was deemed appropriate. The results from the feasibility studies conducted as part of the development of the intervention gave no reason to differentiate or weight one or several variables over the others. An equally weighted additive composite score outlining levels of implementation fidelity was constructed adding the score from each of the four variables

¹ Measured in days

² Measured in weeks

³ Negative numbers denotes days before the 6-month mark, and positive numbers denotes days after the 6-month mark.

Additional file 1

measuring adherence. The composite variable was scored on a 9-point scale from minimum 0 to maximum 8. The composite variable values of 0-2 represents low fidelity, 3-5 represents medium fidelity, and 6-8 represents high fidelity (Table 2).

Table 2 Composite fidelity score

Variable	Low fidelity	Medium fidelity	High fidelity
Composite fidelity score	0-2	3-5	6-8